

CORPORATE CAPTURE OF ENERGY COMMUNITIES

A threat for a citizens
energy transition in Europe

**REPORT COMMISSIONED BY
FRIENDS OF THE EARTH EUROPE,
WITH THE SUPPORT OF THE
EUROPEAN UNION**

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Design: Blush Design Agency

Date: February 2025

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Section 1

INTRODUCTION

Europe's energy transition is witnessing a surge in grassroots initiatives known as energy communities, empowering local residents to actively engage in producing and distributing renewable energy.

These communities, fostered by European and national political and legislative efforts, aim to democratize the energy system by enabling collective citizen participation. This not only fosters social acceptance and empowers individuals but also unlocks access to financing and cultivates **innovative business models**. Ultimately, community energy holds the potential to transform the current energy system from an **oligopoly** controlled by a few powerful companies to a **commons** managed by and for the benefit of local communities.

This movement gained significant momentum in 2019 when the EU finalized the **Clean energy for all Europeans** package, establishing the concepts of **Citizen Energy Communities** (CECs) and **Renewable Energy Communities** (RECs). Driven by the desire to empower consumers and democratize the energy market, the legislation aimed to give individuals and communities a greater voice in the energy transition. The EU **Directive on common rules for the internal electricity market** (2019/944) (IMED) granted consumers, both individually and through CECs, the right to participate in all electricity markets by generating, consuming, sharing, selling electricity, or providing flexibility services. Furthermore, the revised **Renewable Energy Directive** (2018/2001/EU) (RED) strengthened the role of RECs, which differ from CECs in several key aspects. RECs adhere to stricter requirements regarding proximity (local participation), autonomy, and eligibility (shareholders or members limited to natural persons, SMEs, or local authorities), primarily focusing on expanding renewable energy sources.

Conversely, CECs have no geographical constraints, encompass all energy technologies, and have more flexible eligibility criteria, but confine their activities to electricity.

Despite a June 2021 **deadline for transposition**, the **implementation** of these directives across EU member states has been fragmented. This inconsistency stems from different ways for interpreting the legal definition for energy communities. Some countries, like **Sweden**, lag in incorporating these definitions into their national legislation. Others have opted for a superficial approach, merely replicating the EU directives without providing clarity or establishing a supportive framework. Conversely, countries like **Ireland, France, and Italy** have adopted clearer definitions and developed legal frameworks and support mechanisms for energy communities, to different extents, seeking to facilitate the growth of energy communities by creating conditions where they can compete with traditional energy players

However, this progress is threatened by the looming risk of **corporate capture**. Large **energy companies** and **industrial consumers** are exploiting **regulatory loopholes** and ambiguous definitions to gain control of these initiatives. This appropriation allows them to reap benefits at the expense of citizen-led energy communities, circumvent environmental regulations, stifle competition, and secure advantageous feed-in tariffs. A paradigm example for that is **Greece**, which, for instance, initially pioneered the concept of energy communities with law 4513/2018, incorporating most EU criteria. However, commercial entities exploited the framework for their gain (REScoop.eu. (n.d.)). To counter this, a new Law 5037/2023 in 2023 introduced stricter definitions for CECs and RECs, and capped profit distribution at 20% for communities benefiting from priority grid access or financial support, among other measures oriented to avoid corporate capture (Cots, 2024).

The inherent challenge lies in **defining energy communities at a national level** without a pre-existing model, especially when the introduction of incentives is tied to this loose definition. This lack of clarity creates an opening for **capture by entities** that may not embody the true spirit of community energy, potentially diverting resources away from genuine grassroots initiatives.

Without a clear framework, it becomes difficult to distinguish between projects that prioritize collective benefits and those that simply exploit the system for financial gain. In this context, it is crucial that national legislations adhere to the **principles established in the directives** (non-commercial purpose, open and voluntary participation, eligibility to participate, effective control and autonomy or democratic governance) that ultimately define energy communities. These principles ensure that energy communities remain true to their **core values** of local ownership, democratic control, and social benefit. By aligning national legislation with these principles, policymakers can create a regulatory environment that fosters the development of genuine community energy projects while mitigating the risk of capture and ensuring that the benefits of energy communities are widely shared.

This report delves into the **multifaceted nature of corporate capture** within the **energy community** model, examining the enabling conditions and proposing recommendations both for policy makers and energy communities to ensure the respect of these principles.

To achieve this, the report follows a **multi-pronged approach**. Firstly, it establishes a foundational **understanding of corporate capture**, exploring its underlying mechanisms and manifestations. This includes a specific focus on:

- **Lobbying and policy influence:** The influence of large corporations on policymaking and regulatory frameworks can create an uneven playing field that favors corporate interests over community-led initiatives. This can manifest in various ways, such as lobbying for regulations that benefit large-scale projects over smaller community-based ones or influencing the design of subsidy schemes to favor corporate participation.
- **Exploitation of incentives and preferential treatment:** While subsidies and other types of incentives and preferential treatment (for instance, priority accessing the grid) can play a crucial role in supporting the development of energy communities, their design and implementation can inadvertently create opportunities for corporate capture. This can occur when support schemes favor larger entities or projects that prioritize profit maximization over community benefits. Furthermore, a lack of transparency and accountability in subsidy allocation processes can increase the risk of corporate influence and favoritism.

- **Misleading claims and “citizen washing”:** The misuse of the “energy community” label for marketing purposes can mislead consumers and undermine the genuine goals of community energy. This practice often involves large energy companies promoting projects or services that lack true community ownership or control, perhaps no energy community at all (i.e. no legal form), exploiting the positive connotations of the term “energy community” to attract customers and gain market share. This not only misrepresents the nature of these projects but can also create confusion and distrust among consumers, hindering the development of authentic community energy initiatives.

Secondly, the report adopts a **principles-based approach to identify risks** associated with each defining characteristic of energy communities and emphasizes the critical need for robust **oversight mechanisms**. To ensure transparency and accountability, **regulatory authorities** must have the power to verify that energy communities genuinely meet legal requirements. This includes accessing documents like **ownership structures** and **energy data**, conducting audits, and investigating complaints. Authorities should also be able to impose penalties on companies engaging in misleading advertising or failing to meet the criteria for operating as an energy community.

The **case studies** of potential corporate capture analyzed in this report have been gathered through a combination of **desk research** in academic and grey literature, and a **questionnaire** conducted in 2024 by Friends of the Earth Europe, in collaboration with Greenpeace CEE, addressed to the European Civil Society movement. This questionnaire aimed to gather information on instances where for-profit entities might be undermining citizen-led efforts by co-opting the concept of energy communities or capturing resources for their benefit. The goal was to map how this phenomenon occurs across different countries and to identify the underlying causes and structural gaps that enable it. Key information gathered through the questionnaire was then cross-checked and validated through in-depth interviews with respondents.

By exploring these critical areas and offering targeted recommendations, this report aims to contribute to a **policy landscape** that fosters the authentic development of energy communities. The report concludes by elaborating the main conclusions and key findings.

Section 2

CORPORATE CAPTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF ENERGY COMMUNITIES

“Corporate capture” describes how incumbent actors, in this case large energy companies, employ strategies to maintain their market dominance and prevent transformative change. (Pel 2016; Späth, Rohrer, and von Radecki 2015;)

For instance, Pel (2016) suggests that corporate capture arises when less powerful actors, like community groups, try to bring about significant change. Larger, more influential actors, such as established energy companies, might not share the same transformative goals. These powerful actors can **hijack the change process** by framing alternative solutions that distort the original intent. This interaction forces both sides to adapt, leading to a compromise where the initial vision of change is diluted and the meaning of the proposed solutions shifts.

Essentially, **established energy corporations** are inherently inclined to **preserve the existing power structures** within the energy system, meaning they want to retain control over energy production, supply and distribution (Kivimaa et al. 2019; Strachan et al. 2015). These actors maintain their dominance by adopting the **language of change** while subtly redirecting it to serve their own interests (Tilsted et al. 2022). In the energy sector, this can be seen in how companies use rhetoric to downplay truly disruptive solutions and appease those dissatisfied with the current system, all without altering their fundamental practices (Wright et al. 2022).

This body of research suggests that the **narratives of transformation** promoted by large energy corporations may be a **smokescreen**, concealing actions that prevent transformative change in the energy system, without truly shifting the balance of power (Stirling, 2014). In the context of energy communities, this involves **appropriating citizen-led initiatives**, often driven by financial incentives and a desire to control the evolving energy landscape. This can manifest through **influencing policy and regulations** or directly **controlling community energy** projects (Harnett, 2024).

While many energy corporations initially showed limited interest in participatory energy models, the EU’s **Clean Energy Package** (CEP), with its provisions for energy communities and the promise of financial aids and public support, has incentivized their involvement (Fina, and Fechner 2021; Krug et al. 2023). This raises concerns about the **erosion of community ownership and control**, given the inherent power imbalance between corporations and local communities in a market which is characterized by its technical complexity and the need of having a very strong financial umbrella. **Traditional market actors** have been pushing for broader definitions of **“citizen energy communities”** during the transposition process, despite these risks. This could weaken the impact of recognizing **non-commercial groups** who need support to enter the market. Furthermore, by including large energy companies and industrial consumers in a concept originally meant to empower citizens, public trust could be damaged, leading to a form of **“citizen washing”** where these companies appear more community-focused than they truly are (Harnett, 2024).

In this context, **the lack of clear definitions** of energy communities in the CEP and in the transposition in national legislations, particularly regarding membership and ownership, coupled with **weak regulatory oversight and enforcement**, creates opportunities for exploitation by corporations (Bauwens et al. 2016). Other factors that may contribute to this situation are **lack of transparency and information asymmetry**. In fact, limited transparency in operations and decision-making, coupled with corporations’ greater knowledge and expertise in navigating complex energy markets, can lead to communities making **uninformed decisions** that ultimately favor corporate interests (Dóci et al. 2015).

An underlying issue is that **while self consumption schemes or other renewable energy business models can be promoted at policy level, the label “energy community,” with its associated benefits and support, should be reserved for initiatives truly embodying its core principles**. This means genuine community ownership, prioritizing local benefits and sustainability, and ensuring democratic governance. Allowing large energy companies to claim this designation without adhering to these principles undermines the concept. It could lead to unfair competition, greenwashing, and loss of public trust. Clear criteria are vital to ensure only authentic energy communities receive the recognition and support they deserve, fostering truly community-driven energy solutions.

Ideally, energy communities seek to contribute to create a fairer energy system by redistributing power from large energy companies to local communities, empowering people and promoting local ownership. Therefore, the **corporate capture of energy communities** poses a significant threat to this discourse, leading to the erosion of community ownership and control, reduced community benefits, the undermining of social and environmental goals, and a loss of public trust (Harnett, 2024).

Addressing this issue requires a **multi-faceted approach**. This includes **strengthening legal frameworks** with clearer definitions of energy communities that prioritize genuine community ownership, enhancing **regulatory oversight** with robust monitoring and enforcement, promoting **transparency and accountability**, and ensuring that financial incentives prioritize community-led initiatives with safeguards against corporate capture.

2.1 LOBBYING AND POLICY INFLUENCE

As incumbent actors, large energy corporations possess substantial resources and political influence, which they can leverage to shape the transposition process of energy community definitions and enabling frameworks to their advantage. This influence can manifest in various ways, ultimately undermining the transformative potential of community-led energy initiatives.

Firstly, corporations may engage in lobbying efforts to **dilute the core principles enshrined in the definition of energy communities**. This can involve advocating for less stringent membership requirements, thereby allowing for greater corporate involvement and potentially enabling them to dominate decision-making processes. Furthermore, they may push for an emphasis on financial profitability over social and environmental goals, effectively shifting the focus away from community empowerment and towards market-driven objectives.

Secondly, **corporate lobbying can result in the weakening of enabling frameworks** that are crucial for the development of independent energy communities. This can include advocating for limited public funding or complex application processes that disproportionately favor large-scale projects over smaller, community-led initiatives. By influencing grid connection rules, they can further prioritize established energy corporations and hinder the integration of decentralized community energy generation, thus stifling competition and maintaining their control over the energy landscape.

Moreover, large energy corporations can utilize their influence to **shape the narrative surrounding energy communities**, promoting a vision that aligns with their interests. This can involve co-opting the language of empowerment while subtly promoting models that maintain corporate control, effectively masking their self-serving agenda behind a veneer of community participation. They may also actively discourage truly disruptive solutions that challenge the centralized energy system, thereby preserving their dominance and limiting the transformative potential of community-led initiatives.

Furthermore, **corporate influence** can extend to the **creation of alternative concepts and definitions** that deviate from the EU framework. This can manifest in the emergence of “energy community adjacent” concepts, such as “industrial energy communities” (as seen in Hungary), which may blur the lines between genuine community-led initiatives and industry-dominated projects.

By promoting these alternative frameworks, energy corporation can create loopholes and exceptions that allow them to participate in – and potentially control – initiatives designed to empower local communities. This tactic further undermines the original intent of the Clean Energy Package and risks diluting the core principles of democratic governance, local ownership, and social benefit.

The consequences of such corporate capture are far-reaching and detrimental to the goals of the Clean Energy Package, since the social and environmental benefits of energy communities may be diminished, with a greater focus on **corporate profits**.

In 2022, the Association for Hungarian Energy Communities and Flexibility Providers (MERSZ) was established to represent both aggregators and energy communities. MERSZ’s rules allow the leading partner of a government-granted pilot energy community to join the association before that community is officially registered. As the application process for these pilot projects was designed in a way that favored established energy companies over community-driven initiatives, most of the pilot projects, and subsequently MERSZ members, are companies, not citizen groups. Of the eleven members in its “Energy Community” branch, the majority are for-profit companies, including major players like E.ON, STS Group, ON-Energy, PannonWatt, and Capitol Consulting.

Source: Friends of the Earth Survey on Corporate Capture (2024)

As evidenced by Eurogas’s call for supportive measures in the Gas Directive Revision, major energy companies, like E.On and Engie, actively explored how to leverage energy communities for commercial gain and expand their service offerings including this concept in the proposal. This marked a shift from their previous opposition to energy communities during the Clean Energy Package negotiations. In fact, the definition of energy communities that they were pursuing in the Gas Directive Revision included large energy companies, to join and potentially dominate them. Happily, the Parliament and the Council ultimately agreed to delete the citizen energy community concept from the text.

Source: Rescoop (2024)

2.2 PURSUE OF INCENTIVES AND PREFERENTIAL TREATMENT

The rise of energy communities has presented a unique opportunity for many actors, unfortunately also for large corporations, driven by the increasing availability of financial support. This support comes from various sources. Governments are increasingly establishing dedicated public funding to help energy communities overcome initial financial hurdles. This funding assists with early-stage project planning, including setting up a legal entity, conducting feasibility studies, and obtaining technical expertise. It can also provide guarantees or low/zero-interest loans for construction, preferential treatment in accessing the grid, and expedited permitting processes. Furthermore, various **EU funds**, like the **Recovery and Resilience Facility, Structural Funds, and Cohesion Funds**, can be utilized to jumpstart energy communities. These funds often support capacity building and access to expertise throughout project development.

While energy communities existed before the adoption of the **Clean Energy Package**, they primarily operated as citizen-led initiatives with limited corporate involvement. However, the Clean Energy Package, which requires Member States to establish supportive frameworks for energy communities, including **financial incentives and subsidies**, has changed the landscape. These incentives are tremendously important to allow energy communities to compete with traditional actors in the electricity market, but they have also **attracted the attention of energy corporations and created collateral effects**. Essentially, aligning with the energy community model now increases the chances of securing funding. This has led to a surge of corporate interest, with companies utilizing their resources and expertise to adapt their projects accordingly. There’s a risk that large companies may try to dominate these community-led projects, primarily to access funding and advance their own agendas, potentially sidelining the original goals of these initiatives.

To prevent corporate dominance in energy communities, some countries are refining their regulatory approaches to funding allocation. **Germany**, for example, now exempts certain **community-led renewable energy projects** from competitive auctions, recognizing their unique nature and aiming to provide them with easier access to funding. This exemption applies to smaller wind turbines (up to 6 MW) and those owned by citizen energy companies (up to 18 MW). To safeguard against exploitation of this exemption, Germany has implemented stringent criteria for defining citizen energy companies, emphasizing genuine community involvement, democratic decision-making, and local control, as outlined in the **Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG)**. However, it remains to be seen whether these criteria strike the right balance between preventing corporate capture and enabling the growth of community energy.

Similarly, **Greece's 2023 energy law (Law 5037/2023)** introduced measures to prevent abuse of the energy community model. It mandates a minimum number of members and limits profit distribution for communities receiving grid priority access or financial support. These measures aim to curb past instances where large energy companies and investors exploited the system for financial gain, undermining the goals of community-led initiatives.

While these **legislative changes in Germany and Greece** demonstrate a growing awareness of the potential for corporate capture, their effectiveness in achieving the desired balance remains to be evaluated. It is crucial to monitor the impact of these regulations and ensure they effectively prevent corporate dominance without unduly hindering the development of genuine community energy projects. This highlights the ongoing need for adaptive policymaking and continuous evaluation.

Repsol, a major Spanish energy company, indirectly manages over 30% of the European subsidies for energy communities in **Spain**. Specifically, €24.3 million from the Next Generation funds, intended to support citizen-driven energy communities, have been allocated to projects involving Repsol subsidiaries. These subsidiaries manage 28 out of the 151 projects that have received **CE-Implementa** grants. Edinor, Repsol's renewable energy branch, handles 15 of the subsidized communities (€9.9 million), while Ekiluz, a joint venture with the Mondragon Corporation, promotes 13 initiatives (€14.4 million).

Although Edinor and Ekiluz don't directly receive these funds as they are not members of the energy communities, they play significant roles as managers, promoters, designers, or technology partners. In fact, 60% of the subsidies granted in the latest CE-Implementa call (December 2023) went to projects connected to Repsol.

This raises concerns about potential corporate influence within these supposedly community-led initiatives. Repsol's subsidiaries may be exerting significant control over strategic decisions, despite not being formal members.

Sources: Muñoz-Padrós and Marcos (2024, April 14); and Friends of the Earth Survey on Corporate Capture (2024)

Recently in 2024 **Hungary** launched three pilot programs to fund community energy projects, but it seems most of the money went to large companies instead of local communities.

The first program had about 5 million euros to distribute. Five out of the seven winning projects were led by for-profit companies, with each receiving at least 500,000 euros. These companies included the state-owned utility **MVM**, the energy trader Ewiser, the solar panel installer Danubia, Capital Consulting, and energy trader VPP Hungary. Only two projects were led by community-focused groups, but they received much less funding.

The second program, with 10 million euros available, showed a similar trend. Nine out of fifteen winning projects were led by for-profit companies, including big energy utilities like **MVM** and **E.ON**, solar panel companies, and energy software companies. The rest went to municipalities and public bodies, with no funding for community groups or cooperatives.

In the third program, all 33 million euros were given directly to a single charity, the **Maltese Order**, without any competitive process. While they plan to install solar panels and help low-income households, there's no community involvement in the project.

Source: Friends of the Earth survey on Corporate Capture, 2024

Greece's Apollon program, designed to combat energy poverty and reduce municipal energy costs, funded by the Recovery and Resilience Fund (RRF), is focusing on the development of 10-year **Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs)** between private energy providers and regional CECs. This model relegates communities to a passive consumer role since they do not hold ownership and control over renewable energy generation and storage.

As a consequence, municipalities, despite being members of the CECs, are denied any management role in projects, which are instead implemented by private entities selected through tenders outside of community control. This approach raises concerns about transparency and accountability, potentially channeling public funds, including the **€100 million** earmarked for energy communities in the Greek Recovery Plan, towards other initiatives that are not genuine, citizen-inclusive, EU-definitions-aligned energy communities.

While the Apollon program's goals of mitigating energy poverty are commendable, the program's reliance on private investors and centralized project implementation risks undermining social acceptance and community ownership, raising serious concerns about its adherence to the principles of genuine energy communities.

Source: Electra Energy. (2024, November)

2.3 MISLEADING CLAIMS AND “CITIZEN WASHING”

Even if self-called energy communities that don't adhere to the principles of community ownership, local control, and democratic governance don't receive financial aid or subsidies, they can still misuse the “energy community” label for marketing purposes. This tactic, which can be considered a form of “citizen washing,” involves presenting a project as a genuine energy community to attract customers and gain a competitive advantage, even if it doesn't truly meet the criteria of authentic community energy. This practice **misleads consumers and undermines the trust in and development of genuine community-led initiatives**. It exploits the positive image associated with community empowerment and local engagement for commercial gain, without genuinely embodying those principles.

This misleading portrayal can take various forms, such as:

- **Exaggerating community involvement:** Companies may claim that their projects are community-owned or controlled, even if the community has limited decision-making power or ownership stake.
- **Misrepresenting benefits:** They might overstate the social and economic benefits to the local community, creating unrealistic expectations.
- **Using vague or misleading language:** Companies may use terms like “community-based” or “locally driven” without clearly defining what those terms mean in practice.

To address this issue, the European Union has mechanisms in place to protect consumers from misleading claims. These mechanisms are primarily enshrined in two key directives:

- **Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (UCPD):** This directive prohibits unfair commercial practices, including misleading actions or omissions that deceive or are likely to deceive the average consumer. It provides a framework for assessing misleading claims, including those related to social and community aspects, and empowers enforcement authorities to take action against companies that engage in such practices.
- **Directive on Consumer Rights (CRD):** This directive strengthens consumer protection by requiring clear and transparent information about products and services. It mandates that companies provide accurate and understandable information about the ownership, governance, and benefits of energy communities, enabling consumers to make informed decisions.

These directives, and their transpositions into national frameworks, empower consumers and enable enforcement authorities to take action against companies that misuse the “energy community” label or make false claims. However, given the novelty of the energy community concept, further clarification and guidance are needed to effectively apply these directives. This includes developing specific **guidelines** that outline **how the UCPD and CRD apply to energy community advertising**, accompanied by practical examples of acceptable and unacceptable practices. Additionally, clear orientation on which type of information should be disclosed would be helpful, specifying the types of information that must be included in advertisements, such as ownership structure, governance arrangements, benefit-sharing mechanisms, and community involvement.

In this sense, the recently adopted **Directive on Green Claims** strengthens the framework for combating greenwashing, including misleading claims related to environmental sustainability and social responsibility. This directive requires companies to substantiate their environmental claims with robust evidence and prohibits vague or unsubstantiated assertions. In the context of energy communities, this directive can play a role in preventing companies from exploiting the “community” label for greenwashing purposes.

In **Portugal**, major energy companies like EDP¹ and Cleanwatts² are promoting what they claim to be energy communities. However, a closer look reveals a discrepancy between these claims and the reality of the projects. As of June 2023, an analysis of licensing applications in Portugal showed that 95% of the projects were collective self-consumption schemes, while only 5% met the criteria for true energy communities. This distinction is crucial. While both models involve sharing energy, collective self-consumption is primarily a technical arrangement where at least two consumers share the energy produced.

In contrast, a renewable energy community, as defined by the European Union, must be a legal entity with open participation, democratic governance, and a focus on community benefits beyond mere financial profit. Many projects promoted as “energy communities” by these companies, where they retain investment, ownership, and management control, fall short of these criteria. This raises concerns about potentially misleading advertising and the need for greater transparency in the sector.

Sources: Harnett (2024), Sequeira (2024) and Friends of the Earth survey on Corporate Capture (2024)

1 <https://www.edp.com/en/news/edp-creates-solar-energy-community-caldas-da-rainha-involving-over-200-companies-and-families>

2 <https://cleanwatts.energy>

In **Spain**, Repsol highlights its “Solar Communities” on its website, emphasizing the benefits and ease of joining these communities, even though they are examples of third party CSC, not genuine energy communities that strictly follow all the principles mentioned in the report.

Source: <https://www.repsol.com/en/energy-and-the-future/future-of-the-world/solar-communities/index.cshtml> and Harnett (2024)

Section 3

A PRINCIPLES-BASED APPROACH FOR CITIZENS ENERGY COMMUNITIES

To effectively analyze the various ways corporations may hinder the principles encapsulated by the energy community definition contained in the Directives, this study adopts a structured approach focused on the core principles that define genuine energy communities

This approach allows for a systematic examination of how corporate capture manifests in practice, even when formal compliance with regulations may appear to be met. By dissecting **case studies** through the lens of each principle, we can pinpoint the specific pressure points where corporate influence undermines the community-led ethos of energy initiatives.

The following sections delve into each of these principles, drawing on **data analysis** and **case study** findings to expose the tactics used by corporations to circumvent the spirit and intent of the **REC and IMED Directives**. This analysis will be structured around the following key principles:

- **Non-commercial purpose:** Examining how the prioritization of community benefits over financial profits is upheld or compromised.
- **Open and voluntary participation:** Investigating whether membership and engagement within energy communities are truly open and accessible to all.

- **Eligibility to participate:** Assessing whether participation criteria are designed to promote genuine community involvement instead of favoring corporate interests.
- **Effective control:** Analyzing the extent to which decision-making power resides with local citizens or is unduly influenced by corporate actors.
- **Autonomy:** Examining the extent to which energy communities are independent of external influence and control, particularly from large energy companies.

By systematically analyzing each principle, this report aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the diverse manifestations of corporate capture and offer targeted policy recommendations to safeguard the integrity of the energy community movement.

However, it's crucial to clarify our **interpretation of "risk"** in this context. When we identify a specific factor – such as high capital entry requirements – as potentially increasing the risk of corporate capture, we are not suggesting that all instances of high capital entry requirements inevitably lead to corporate capture. Nor are we implying that energy communities with low capital entry requirements are automatically immune to this phenomenon. Instead, we aim to highlight **potential vulnerabilities** within the energy community model. Certain characteristics can create an environment more susceptible to corporate influence. This is because such requirements may favor larger, well-resourced entities that are primarily profit-driven, potentially hindering the participation of smaller actors and genuine community-led initiatives.

Similarly, the **choice of legal form** for energy communities can also influence the risk of corporate capture. Allowing them to be structured as profit-driven entities, like joint-stock companies, can prioritize profit maximization over community benefits, since the decision making powers in these legal forms are tied to capital ownership rather than democratic principles of one person, one vote, creating inherent incentives that favor profit distribution to members over reinvestment or the pursuit of social and environmental goals. This doesn't mean that all energy communities structured as joint-stock companies may automatically become examples of corporate capture, but it does introduce a potential vulnerability that warrants careful consideration.

On the other hand, it's important to acknowledge that the **infringement of principles**, such as autonomy and effective control, are more directly linked to the corporate capture phenomenon. These principles go to the essence of the corporate capture concept, since they address fundamental issues like who holds control and who exercises influence within the energy community. For instance, in RECs, effective control must be exercised by members located in proximity to the community's renewable energy projects. Therefore, infringement of these principles may weigh more heavily than infringement of other principles when determining if a case of corporate capture has occurred, sending a stronger signal in this direction.

The **Bicesse kindergarten project**, advertised as an "inclusive energy community" by **Greenvolt Comunidades** (a subsidiary of the Greenvolt group), located in **Portugal**, aimed to address energy poverty by providing renewable energy to vulnerable groups in the vicinity of the kindergarten as part of a corporate social responsibility strategy of the company. The anchor member (owner of the space where the renewables were installed) of this project was **Santa Casa da Misericórdia da Cascais (SCMC)**, a non-profit institution that receives public and private funding to provide kindergartens to lower-income groups.

The consumer members were selected by SCMC based on economic and social vulnerability criteria, in consultation with **Greenvolt**. However, Greenvolt and the anchor member retained ownership and control of the renewable energy system, while citizens were essentially consumers rather than active participants. While the project undoubtedly provided social and environmental benefits by addressing energy poverty and promoting renewable energy, the lack of a community organisation and the consequent lack of effective control by the "citizens/users" undermines the core principles of community ownership and democratic governance that define genuine energy communities.

Therefore, in this case the infringement of the effective control principle and the lack of a constitution of a formal organisation is more significant when assessing whether it constitutes corporate capture than the provision of social and environmental benefits or respect for the non commercial purpose principle.

Source: Harnett, 2024

However, in this report, we have opted for a **comprehensive approach** to include the **risks associated with each principle**, even if they are more indirect, keeping in mind that **identifying these risks** is not about making absolute **judgments or generalizations**. Rather, it's about recognizing potential red flags and understanding the factors that can increase the likelihood of corporate capture. This nuanced approach allows for a more comprehensive assessment of the energy community landscape and enables the development of targeted safeguards to protect the integrity and purpose of this movement. Finally, this analysis will also address the mechanisms of control employed to ensure the implementation of the above-mentioned principles, such as registration processes, and monitoring bodies, as a key element in preventing corporate capture.

3.1 NON-COMMERCIAL PURPOSE

The primary goal of energy communities, as defined by the European Union's **Clean Energy Package**, is to deliver **benefits** to their members and the local community, rather than maximizing financial returns. These benefits can be **environmental**, such as reducing carbon emissions and promoting renewable energy sources; social, such as fostering community cohesion through the **empowerment of citizens** to collaboratively develop projects of local significance, promoting education and awareness, and addressing **energy poverty**; or **economic**, such as lowering energy costs for members and creating local jobs (Roberts, 2020).

While energy communities can generate economic **profit**, and provide a return on investment to members, this should be a **secondary objective**. Revenues obtained from engaging in market activities should be primarily **reinvested back** into the community to fund new projects, improve energy efficiency, support educational initiatives, or provide assistance to vulnerable households (Energy Community Secretariat, 2024). This focus on **community well-being** distinguishes energy communities from traditional energy companies driven by profit maximization.

RISKS OF CORPORATE CAPTURE

One of the main risks associated with this principle is the **choice of legal form**. Allowing energy communities to be structured as profit-driven entities, like joint-stock companies, can prioritize profit maximization over community benefits and potentially lead to exploitation of support mechanisms. To avoid this, some Member States specify certain legal forms, often favoring those that promote cooperative, social economy, or non-profit objectives. However, it's important to balance this with the need for financial sustainability and the ability to attract investment. Allowing limited profit sharing or disbursements to members can incentivize participation and enable larger projects. Even if the choice of legal form is left open, the requirement to comply with EU principles is intended to mitigate the potential for prioritizing profit over community benefit. However, this reliance on compliance alone can make it more challenging to ensure genuine community focus, as it necessitates robust monitoring and enforcement mechanisms.

It's also important to distinguish between two key aspects of financial viability:

- **Turnover:** This refers to the revenue generated by the energy community through its activities, such as selling electricity or providing energy services. Generating turnover is essential for any organization to be financially sustainable and cover operational costs.
- **Return on Investment:** This relates to the financial gains that members or investors receive on their initial investment in the energy community. Allowing for a reasonable return on investment can incentivize participation and attract necessary capital for larger projects.

Such disbursements to members, within reasonable limits, should not disqualify an energy community from being recognized as a citizen or renewable energy community. Furthermore, banning disbursements altogether could hinder the financing of larger projects, limiting the potential impact of community energy. Therefore, finding the right balance between promoting community benefit and allowing for financial viability is essential for fostering the growth of genuine and sustainable energy communities.

Member states have used different approaches in their transpositions to prioritize community benefits over profits for energy communities:

- **Strict non-profit models:** Some countries, like **Croatia**, and **Lithuania**, explicitly forbid profit-making or restrict energy communities to non-profit legal structures.
- **Limited profit distribution:** Others, such as **Slovakia** and **Greece**, allow some profit generation but mandate that a significant portion be reinvested into the community or used for reserves. For instance, the 2023 law in Greece established a 20% limit on the profits that can be distributed to the members of the energy communities if they take advantage of priority access to the grid or are eligible for financial support.
- **Purpose-driven approach:** **Belgium** and **Latvia** emphasize the community's primary purpose in their statutes, ensuring that profit motives remain secondary to community goals.
- **Specific legal entities:** Some countries like **Hungary** promote community focus by limiting the allowed legal entities to cooperatives and non-profit companies.

Source: European Commission (2023a)

Another risk is the **election of the business model**.

Corporations may prioritize business models that are profitable but don't necessarily align with community needs or desires, marketing them as "energy communities", even though these models often don't even create formal organizations, which is a fundamental requirement for being recognized as an energy community under the EU framework. They simply represent decentralized energy production and consumption arrangements, falling short of the core principles of community ownership, democratic governance, and social benefit. For instance, third party **Collective Self Consumption (CSC)** relies on a **Power Purchase Agreement (PPA)**, which is essentially a long-term energy contract. In this arrangement, a client agrees to purchase electricity, at a fixed price, from an energy provider who installs a renewable energy system, like solar panels, on the client's property. The energy provider takes care of all the initial hurdles, including the upfront investment, securing permits, installation, and ongoing management of the system. Since the energy company retains control, the users have little influence over decisions regarding the system's operation, maintenance, or technology. This can lead to disengagement and prevent the community from tailoring the system to its needs.

In **Portugal**, several for-profit energy companies (e.g., EDP, Greenvolt, Cleanwatts) are misrepresenting themselves as providers of "Energy Community" products to attract new and existing clients. However, these offerings are merely examples of third-party CSC models, which fall short of the true definition of energy communities. While third party CSC arrangements offer consumers access to clean energy at a fixed price, they significantly limit community participation and benefits. Essentially, these models relegate communities to the role of passive consumers, depriving them of opportunities to generate revenue by selling excess energy or participating in demand response programs. This lack of ownership can also diminish engagement in energy conservation efforts, as the community may feel less responsibility for the system's efficiency. Ultimately, third party CSC models offer limited social, economic, and environmental benefits compared to genuine energy communities where citizens actively participate in ownership and decision-making processes.

Source: Harnett (2024) and Friends of the Earth Survey on Corporate Capture (2024)

3.2 OPEN AND VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

The principle of **open and voluntary participation** means that energy communities should be accessible to all who wish to join and that membership should always be a free choice, without arbitrary or discriminatory restrictions (Roberts, 2020). This ensures that the benefits of community energy are accessible to a wide range of individuals and entities, promoting social inclusion and broad participation in the energy transition (Hoops, 2021). However, the level of openness can be adjusted depending on the specific context of the energy community. For example, a community might require members to live in the same area where the community operates. This makes sense because the community's activities, like sharing energy from local solar panels, are likely focused on that specific area.

Voluntary participation means that individuals and entities should have the freedom to join or leave an energy community without facing undue pressure or penalties (Energy Communities Secretariat, 2024). This respects individual autonomy and ensures that participation is based on genuine interest and commitment. While the right to leave is essential, energy communities may implement reasonable rules to manage membership changes, especially when it comes to investment and shareholding. For example, requiring members to maintain their investment for a specific period can help ensure the stability and long-term viability of community projects (Energy Communities Secretariat, 2024). However, such restrictions should be balanced with the members' right to withdraw and should not be excessively burdensome.

RISKS OF CORPORATE CAPTURE

While embracing open participation is vital for fostering inclusive energy communities, an **excessively broad interpretation of “openness” can inadvertently open the door to corporate capture**, jeopardizing the fundamental purpose of grassroots energy initiatives. As will be observed in the section on the “eligibility to participate principle”, being too open to all participants in an energy community may conflict with the original goal of empowering people at the local level to take charge of their own energy solutions. If large corporations are permitted to become members, their substantial financial resources and political clout can easily overshadow the voices of individual citizens and smaller stakeholders, potentially leading to decisions that prioritize corporate interests over community needs and priorities. This is all the more relevant for **Citizen Energy Communities (CECs)**, which, unlike Renewable Energy Communities (RECs), are open to all enterprises, not just SMEs. This broader membership scope for CECs increases the risk of corporate dominance and highlights the need for careful consideration of participation rules.

On the other hand, energy communities can set their own rules about who they let in, **as long as the rules are fair and don’t discriminate against anyone**. This allows communities to strike a balance between openness and safeguarding against undue corporate influence, ensuring that the energy community remains truly community-led and focused on achieving its social and environmental goals.

One way corporate capture may manifest, even indirectly, is through the **imposition of high capital entry requirements** for members which can disproportionately impact individuals from lower socio-economic backgrounds, effectively creating an access barrier that contradicts the RED II Directive’s explicit objective of alleviating energy poverty and ensuring accessibility for all consumers, including vulnerable households (Article 22(7)). This can create an environment more susceptible to corporate influence since such requirements may favor larger, well-resourced entities that are primarily profit-driven, potentially hindering the participation of smaller actors and genuine community-led initiatives, even though in some cases it may be justified. Although the Directive mandates accessibility, it provides no concrete definition of what constitutes an “accessible” price, leaving room for interpretation and potential inconsistencies in implementation across Member States.

A review of 570 **German** energy cooperative statutes reveals that the typical minimum investment is 500 euros, with a significant number requiring 1,000 euros or more upfront, highlighting the potential financial barrier to entry for many citizens.

Source: Hoops (2021)

The complexities surrounding **membership rights and exit clauses** present another area vulnerable to corporate capture. While the IMED prioritizes consumer protection, allowing members to maintain relationships with traditional energy suppliers and switch freely, it doesn’t fully address how individuals can exit an energy community. This leaves Member States to define their own rules, leading to potential inconsistencies and loopholes that could be exploited by corporations. While individuals should have the freedom to leave an energy community, these communities also need some control over membership changes to ensure their long-term viability. Requiring members to maintain their investment for a specific period can prevent premature withdrawals that could jeopardize projects or leave the community financially vulnerable. For instance, a corporation could threaten to withdraw its capital, potentially derailing the project, if certain conditions favorable to its interests are not met. However, excessively long waiting periods or complex exit procedures could create barriers for individuals seeking to leave, potentially trapping them in unfavorable terms. To mitigate this risk, a balance must be struck between individual rights and the community’s needs. Ultimately, the goal is to create a framework that protects both individual members and the long-term sustainability of the energy community.

According to press reports, energy communities linked to Ekiluz, an entity born from the alliance of Repsol and the Mondragón group in **Spain**, have imposed a requirement on citizen members of the community that the electricity supplier be Ekiluz itself.

Source: Muñoz-Padrós and Marcos (2024, April 14)

3.3 ELIGIBILITY TO PARTICIPATE

Eligibility to participate in energy communities is a key principle designed to ensure these initiatives remain truly community-driven and accessible. While CECs generally have open membership, RECs prioritize local participation by focusing on natural persons, local authorities, and SMEs. This focus on local involvement helps prevent domination by large energy companies, ensuring that RECs serve the community’s interests rather than commercial gain. Furthermore, Article 22, paragraph 1 of the RED II clarifies that Member States may limit or prohibit participation by **certain private companies whose participation in RECs does constitute their primary commercial or professional activity**.

RISKS OF CORPORATE CAPTURE

The risks and challenges associated with this principle can differ between RECs and CECs. For **RECs**, monitoring eligibility is relatively straightforward, as the RED II Directive clearly defines the types of legal and natural persons allowed to participate, including SMEs, citizens and local administrations (Energy Community Secretariat, 2024). This limits the risk of large energy corporations unduly influencing the community. However, challenges remain in excluding companies whose primary activity is energy-related, while still allowing for collaboration and access to expertise.

As a positive example, **French energy law** generally prevents private companies primarily focused on the energy sector from joining energy communities. However, “citizen intermediation structures” are exempt from this rule. This includes RECs, investment funds authorized to support social entrepreneurship and specializing in renewable energy, and companies dedicated to renewable energy development with “solidarity utility company” status. In essence, while typical energy companies are excluded, organizations prioritizing social and community aspects of renewable energy can participate.

Source: European Commission (2023a)

In contrast, **CECs**, with their more open membership structure, face a higher risk of undue influence by large corporations. These companies could leverage their resources to steer the community’s direction, potentially undermining its community-focused objectives. In this case, strict application of the “effective control” principle (see later) is essential to mitigate this risk, which pretends that decision-making power remains with the community members, preventing entities that are not SMEs, local governments or citizens from exerting undue influence.

While the principle of eligibility to participate in energy communities aims to create inclusive and community-driven initiatives while preventing domination by large energy companies, striking a balance between open access, safeguards against corporate capture, and the need for expertise is crucial for the successful development and sustainability of energy communities. With this regard, overly restrictive rules can also create barriers, especially when specialized expertise is needed for successful project development and long-term sustainability.

With this regard, applying the eligibility principle to RECs requires careful consideration of several factors:

- **Primary commercial or professional activity:** Differentiate between companies whose core business is energy and those with “**incidental**” energy activities. For example, a technology company developing software for energy management could be distinguished from a traditional utility. On the other hand, community-focused energy entities (like existing RECs and CECs) should be allowed to participate in other RECs, as well as its subsidiaries, with careful checks on their ownership, transparency, and alignment with community principles.
- A CEC like “Som Energía” in **Spain** or any of its subsidiaries (for instance, Som Comunitats) should generally be allowed to participate as a member in other RECs or CECs, even if their primary activity is energy, as their community-owned structure and non-profit nature align with REC principles, and their expertise may be essential to help new RECs and CECs navigate through very technical issues such as permitting or financing.

- **Balancing exclusion and expertise** is a delicate act. While excluding large or energy corporations from RECs is essential for preventing corporate capture, in some cases their technical, financial, and operational expertise may be needed, for instance regarding tasks like grid connection, project development, or securing financing, which is not easily accessible. Therefore, **finding ways to collaborate with energy and financial companies (for instance, cooperatives of credit) without compromising this principle** or community control may be necessary where the expertise is unavailable elsewhere, for instance via provisions of technical services. However, relying on professional market actors as intermediaries has potential drawbacks. It can increase costs for energy communities, raise privacy concerns due to data sharing with third parties, and potentially hinder their autonomy and self-sufficiency by reducing the need to develop internal capacity. (European Commission, 2023b).
- **Eligibility criteria** for RECs can pose challenges to existing community energy models that include larger entities, such as cooperative banks in **Germany**, as highlighted by Roberts (2020). Adapting to new requirements may require restructuring and re-organization, potentially impacting their operations and governance. Research indicates that this may necessitate innovative solutions of cooperation that do not compromise the decision-making autonomy of the energy community (Envall and Rohrer, 2024).
- Large corporations could use their **subsidiaries** to fulfill the requirements of eligibility and gain excessive influence or control over energy communities, potentially undermining the democratic and participatory nature of these initiatives. This could lead to decisions that favor the interests of the parent company over those of the community, contradicting the spirit of the eligibility to participate principle. Additionally, the participation of subsidiaries can erode trust in energy communities, as members may perceive them as being controlled by external interests. This can lead to reduced participation and hinder the long-term sustainability of the community.

3.4 EFFECTIVE CONTROL

The principle of effective control in energy communities is crucial to ensure that decision-making power remains with those who are most impacted by the community's activities and aligned with its goals. For **CECs, effective control should be exercised by individuals, local authorities, or small enterprises**, preventing large energy companies from using CECs for their own commercial gain (Energy Communities Secretariat, 2024; Hoops, 2021). The IMED further defines "control" as the ability to exert decisive influence over an undertaking, such as determining the composition of its governing bodies or shaping its key decisions. This approach seeks that CECs remain focused on citizen-led initiatives and local benefits. RECs, on the other hand, should be effectively controlled by members located near the renewable energy projects, empowering those most affected by the installations to make decisions about their operation (Energy Communities Secretariat; Hoops, 2021). While **RECs** can include members from further afield, and energy companies, large enterprises, and non-local authorities cannot be members, **the emphasis of effective control is on maintaining local control** (Roberts, 2020).

RISKS OF CORPORATE CAPTURE

The risks related to corporate capture undermining this principle that should be contemplated are the following:

- Many energy communities have a multi-tiered governance structure, with a General Assembly of members and a Board of Directors. While the Board is ultimately accountable to the Assembly, it typically holds significant power in making key decisions, particularly regarding new renewable energy projects. This can lead to a rather passive General Assembly, even though it's technically the highest decision-making body. This **concentration of power in the Board raises concerns about effective control** and democratic participation and its associated risk of corporate capture. If "effective control" is simply defined as holding a majority of votes in the General Assembly (more than 50%), it could allow situations where citizens and smaller stakeholders have limited influence on the actual management and direction of the community, because the Board could still be underrepresented by them.

This becomes even more problematic when external actors, such as banks or energy suppliers, have guaranteed seats on the Board, further reducing members' influence. To address those issues, certain Member States, such as Belgium (in Brussels-Capital, Flanders, and Wallonia) and Greece, mandate that energy communities explicitly outline in their governing documents how control is distributed and exercised among their members. This requirement promotes transparency and accountability, ensuring clarity on how decisions are made and power is allocated within the community.

Different countries have unique rules to ensure effective control of energy communities by citizens. In Austria, big energy companies are excluded from controlling CECs, and local producers can join RECs as long as they aren't controlled by major energy players. In **Belgium's Brussels-Capital Region**, guidance from the regulatory authority clarifies the concept of control and who can exercise it. **Germany** requires that at least 75% of voting rights in an REC be held by individuals living within 50 km of the project. **Lithuania** mandates that at least three shareholders in a REC must be individuals with voting rights. These diverse approaches reflect the varying interpretations and implementations of the "effective control" principle across Europe.

Source: European Commission (2023a)

- RECs are subject to a **geographic delimitation principle**, meaning their **effective control must be exercised by members located in proximity to the community's renewable energy projects**. This provision aims to ensure that those most directly impacted by the installations have decision-making authority over their development and operation. However, the definition of "proximity" remains subject to interpretation by Member States. An overly narrow interpretation could inadvertently constrain the growth and viability of RECs by limiting the pool of potential members and hindering the aggregation of sufficient capital and expertise. This necessitates a balanced approach that acknowledges the importance of local control while also allowing for flexibility to accommodate the diverse geographical contexts and energy needs across the European Union.

When it comes to defining "local proximity" for RECs, different countries have adopted varied approaches. For instance, in **Finland**, control is determined by membership, effectively linking eligibility to control. **Germany** mandates that at least 75% of voting rights be held by individuals residing within a 50 km radius of the planned installation, with a minimum requirement of 50 individuals as voting shareholders. **Lithuania**, on the other hand, stipulates that a majority of the votes at the shareholders' meeting must belong to individuals living near the REC.

Source: European Commission (2023a)

- Ownership plays a significant role in relation to the effective control principle. While the RED II Directive explicitly links RECs to the **ownership of renewable energy projects**, the IMED remains less explicit regarding ownership requirements for CECs. This discrepancy has led to diverse interpretations across Member States. Many countries mandate ownership of renewable energy assets by energy communities, while others allow for "right of use" arrangements, such as leasing or usufruct agreements, which grant the community operational control over the assets without requiring full ownership. As Barnes et al. (2022) highlight, corporations promoting these models where the external actor, and not the community, retains the ownership, may have "little incentive to help reduce energy expenditure and relinquish control over the means of energy production". This raises concerns about the extent to which it can truly maximize community benefits, particularly those related to community building, collective action, and the development of locally appropriate solutions.

Brussels recognizes three community energy models: CEC and REC, both prioritizing community ownership, and the Local Energy Community (LEC), which allows third-party ownership. While one of the reasons to introduce this model was to allow individuals and companies with existing solar panel installations in rooftops to join LECs by “pooling” and contributing with their solar production, LECs raise concerns about corporate capture, where companies owning the assets could prioritize profits over community benefits, leading to higher prices and limited community control. This could reduce citizens to mere customers instead of active participants in the core of the energy community.

Source: Muñoz Padros, A., & Marcos, J. (2024, September 30)

3.5 AUTONOMY

The principle of autonomy in renewable energy communities under the RED II ensures these entities remain **independent** and driven by the **collective interests** of their members, rather than being dominated by individual members, investors, or external collaborators. Essentially, **autonomy safeguards** against situations where a powerful member or investor could unduly **influence decision-making**, ensuring that the community operates democratically and in the best interests of all members (Hoops, 2021). This principle is rooted in the **cooperative model**, where democratic governance and equal decision-making rights for all members are paramount (Roberts, 2020).

While the IMED doesn't explicitly mention autonomy for CECs, it's implicitly applicable to both CECs and RECs, as both are envisioned as grassroots initiatives driven by citizen participation and cooperation (Hoops, 2021). While related, **autonomy and effective control** are distinct concepts in the context of energy communities. **Effective control** ensures that decision-making power lies in those individuals and entities that are not explicitly excluded by the IMED or the RED Directives, meaning those that are not SMEs, local authorities, or citizens (and in the case of RECs, locals or residents living in the proximity). **Autonomy**, on the other hand, focuses on preventing any single member, investor, or collaborator from exerting undue influence over the community. Unlike effective control, autonomy does not stress the insulation from a potentially harmful category of entities (big corporations, etc.), but from individual members or stakeholders, whatever is their condition, size, etc..It ensures that energy communities operate independently and democratically, reflecting the collective will of their members rather than the interests of a select few (Hoops,2021).

RISKS OF CORPORATE CAPTURE

As stated in Recital 77 of the RED II Directive, RECs should remain independent from individual members or traditional market actors who might exert undue influence through membership, investment, or other forms of cooperation: “to avoid abuse and to ensure broad participation, renewable energy communities should be capable of remaining autonomous from individual members and other traditional market actors that participate in the community as members or shareholders, or who cooperate through other means such as investment.” Therefore, any infringement of this autonomy principle inherently signifies a certain risk of corporate capture, as it undermines the community's ability to operate in the best interests of its members and the local community.

This autonomy has both internal and external dimensions:

- **Internally**, it ensures the community is governed collectively and democratically, representing the will of all members. While some individuals or entities might play a crucial role in driving a community's development, their influence shouldn't overshadow the collective will of the members. In reality, the growth of energy communities often relies on a few dedicated individuals or organizations who provide essential commitment, expertise, and support. These pioneers often drive many activities and exert significant influence on the community's direction. While their contributions are invaluable, their disproportionate influence can pose a challenge to autonomous decision-making. However, discouraging their involvement could stifle collaboration and hinder the success of these communities. This highlights the need for a balanced approach that recognizes the importance of individual initiative while safeguarding the community's autonomy and democratic governance. In this context, autonomy ensures the energy community operates democratically, with decisions reflecting the collective will of its members rather than being dictated by a select few.

Many countries have implemented specific rules to ensure the autonomy of energy communities. For example, in **Ireland**, to qualify as a REC under the Renewable Energy Support Scheme, each shareholder or member has equal voting rights, regardless of their level of investment or ownership stake in the community. **Germany** limits any single member or shareholder to a maximum of 10% of voting rights in a Citizen Energy Company. Similarly, **Croatia** restricts ownership to no more than 40% of the energy community's shares. **Greece** applies autonomy to both RECs and CECs, limiting individual members to 20% of shares (with exceptions for local authorities) and implementing a “one member, one vote” system in the general assembly. **Hungary** prohibits sole or majority control of RECs and CECs by any natural or legal person (except for municipalities). As a negative note, some countries have not integrated the autonomy principle in their transpositions, in violation of EU directives, such as Estonia and Austria.

Source: European Commission (2023a)

- In its **external dimension**, the principle of autonomy is crucial for safeguarding energy communities from undue influence by external actors, even those who don't have voting rights within the community. While collaboration with external entities like financial institutions or technology providers can be beneficial, excessive dependence on their expertise or financial resources can inadvertently erode a community's autonomy. For example, some credit contracts for renewable energy projects may include clauses that allow the lender to temporarily acquire seats on the board of directors if the community fails to meet certain financial obligations. This situation clearly compromises the community's autonomy, as external actors can directly influence its governance and potentially steer its activities towards their own interests. Research highlights the vulnerability of energy communities to such external influence, particularly in the early stages of development when they may lack financial resources or technical expertise (Szabó et al., 2020). In particular, lack of transparency in collaboration agreements and weak regulatory oversight can exacerbate this risk, allowing external actors to exert undue influence without adequate accountability (Bouzarovski et al., 2023).

The **case of Repsol** and its subsidiaries in **Spain** highlights how the **principle of autonomy** can be compromised even with citizen participation in energy communities. Repsol's subsidiaries, Edinor (focused on renewable energy) and Ekiluz (a joint venture with Mondragon Corporation), play a significant role in promoting, designing, and managing energy communities, raising concerns about the actual independence and control exercised by these communities.

In these cases, energy communities are structured as associations (a legal entity) open to local residents living within a 2 km radius of the renewable energy installation and to local authorities. Importantly, neither Repsol's subsidiaries nor the **Chambers of Commerce**, also promoters of the initiative, participate as members of these associations or have voting rights (so there is no infringement of the eligibility to participate or effective control principles). However, the communities rely heavily on Edinor and Ekiluz for technical expertise, administrative support, and strategic orientation as service providers, or as they call it, technological partners. In this regard, concerns remain about the level of influence exerted by Repsol's subsidiaries, particularly when this model has been replicated all across Spain and has received financial support from EU Next Generation Funds.

If we take Edinor (Repsol subsidiary) as an example, it started in Navarra managing as a service provider two networks of **local energy communities** (CEL) called "Toda Navarra I" and "Toda Navarra II" with the collaboration of the Navarra Chamber of Commerce, and the model has spread throughout Spain with the support of other Chambers of Commerce. There are now 55 CELs encompassing 284 localities, under names like Toda Sevilla, Toda Almería, Toda Badajoz, Toda Huesca, Toda Alicante, Toda La Rioja, Toda Valladolid, Toda Badajoz and Toda Cantabria, all of them with Edinor as the service provider.

Source: Muñoz-Padrós and Marcos (2024, April 14); Friends of the Earth Survey on Corporate Capture (2024)

- On the other hand, requiring a **minimum number of members** in an energy community can be an effective way to bolster its autonomy. The idea is simple: with a larger and more diverse membership base, it becomes more difficult for any single individual or entity to exert excessive control or influence over the community's decisions. As highlighted by the European Commission (2023a), while the EU directives provide a minimum harmonization framework, Member States have the flexibility to adopt **additional participation criteria**, such as minimum number of members, to further strengthen community autonomy and align with their specific national objectives.

Different countries have set varying minimum participation requirements for energy communities. In **Germany**, a minimum of 50 individuals are required as voting shareholders. **Lithuania** similarly mandates that at least three shareholders with voting rights must be natural persons. **Austria** requires a minimum of two members or partners for both RECs and CECs. **Greece** has a more tiered approach, with a general minimum of 30 members for RECs. However, this can be reduced to 20 members for communities in smaller island municipalities, 15 members if at least 15 SMEs participate, or just three members if a local authority is involved. Ireland requires at least one shareholder or member to be registered as a "Sustainable Energy Community" with the relevant authority. These diverse approaches reflect the flexibility afforded to Member States in setting participation thresholds that align with their specific contexts and policy objectives.

Source: European Commission (2023a)

3.6 MECHANISMS OF CONTROL

Establishing a robust system for registering and monitoring energy communities is crucial for their successful development. Registration provides a means of validating an initiative's status as a legitimate energy community, requiring the submission of identifying information and founding documents to a public authority. This process not only confirms compliance with legal definitions but also creates a foundation for long-term tracking and analysis of the sector's progress. Monitoring, in turn, allows for tracking the growth and impact of energy communities, identifying barriers to their development, and facilitating a feedback loop between communities, regulators, and policymakers. This feedback is essential for refining policies, adapting support schemes, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of the sector.

However, the importance of registration and monitoring extends beyond mere data collection. It is essential to ensure that registered entities genuinely comply with the legal definition of an energy community and with the above mentioned principles. This requires establishing an authority with the power to scrutinize applications, conduct audits, and investigate complaints. This authority should have the capacity to exclude entities that do not respect the principles, engage in misleading claims or fail to meet the criteria for operating as an energy community, including barring them from accessing subsidies and support schemes.

Member States generally take three approaches to registering energy communities (European Commission, 2023b):

- **Centralized Registry:** Some appoint an authority to maintain a register of energy communities. This allows clear identification and facilitates long-term monitoring.
- **Prequalification Criteria:** Some establish criteria for accessing support schemes for RECs. This can complement a general registration process or serve as a first step while a comprehensive framework is developed.
- **Combined Registration and Licensing:** A few combine registration with licensing for specific energy activities (e.g., energy sharing). This can streamline the process but may lead to overly technical requirements and a misperception of energy communities' socio-economic value (European Commission, 2023b).

1. Centralized Registry

- **Austria:** Energy communities register online via the Coordination Office website after establishing their organizational structure. This registry allows easy identification of RECs and CECs by region.

2. Prequalification Criteria

- **Germany:** DSOs verify compliance with the citizen energy company definition for exemption from tenders for renewable energy projects.
- **Ireland:** RECs must prove to the Ministry that they meet all criteria to participate in the "community-led projects" category of the Renewable Energy Support Scheme (RESS).

3. Combined Registration and Licensing

- **Lithuania:** RECs must obtain a permit to produce electricity from the State Energy Regulatory Council, which also grants them renewable energy community status. Different requirements apply to the founding documents of CECs and RECs.

Source: European Commission (2023b)

Regardless of the approach, demonstrating registration or prequalification requirements should be simple. However, there needs to be a balance between simplicity and ensuring that the requirements are robust enough to verify compliance with core principles and prevent corporate capture. Procedures can be streamlined with existing registration processes, and requirements should be minimal to avoid overburdening communities.

Due to the **Flemish energy regulator (VREG)** lack of power to verify if energy communities registrations truly represent citizen-led initiatives or not, there's a growing trend of large corporations registering as RECs and CECs. Many are financial cooperatives, often subsidiaries of larger companies, like Nuhma NV with its subsidiaries ECO2050, Limburg Wind CV, and Z-Kracht. In concrete terms, only 35 of the 78 entities registered in Flanders have been identified as citizen groups. Of the remaining 43, at least 12 are linked to financial cooperatives (fincoops) or are hybrid models. Banks, construction companies and municipalities, among others, complete this list.

Source: Friends of the Earth Survey on Corporate Capture (2024) and Muñoz Padros, A., & Marcos, J. (2024, September 30)

Section 4

RECOMMENDATIONS

To mitigate the risks of corporate capture and ensure energy communities remain truly community-driven, the following recommendations emerged from the analyses within this report.

These recommendations address key areas of concern, including ensuring transparency and public participation, preventing the exploitation of incentives and preferential treatment, banning misleading claims and “citizen washing,” guaranteeing the non-commercial purpose of energy communities, ensuring open and voluntary participation, defending eligibility criteria, guaranteeing effective control and autonomy, and establishing robust mechanisms of control and oversight. By implementing these recommendations, policymakers and energy communities can create a supportive environment for authentic community energy initiatives.

1. ENSURE TRANSPARENCY AND PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

- Strengthen lobbying transparency rules to expose undue corporate influence on policy making related to energy communities, including mandatory disclosure of lobbying activities and publicly accessible registers of lobbyists.
- Ensure meaningful citizen participation in policymaking processes related to energy communities, including the transposition of EU directives into national legislation. This could include: public consultations and stakeholder engagement, citizen assemblies or deliberative forums and representation of community energy interests on advisory boards or committees.
- Provide resources and support for capacity building within energy communities, empowering them to develop project proposals and secure funding, navigate regulatory processes and advocate for their interests.

2. PREVENT THE EXPLOITATION OF INCENTIVES AND PREFERENTIAL TREATMENT

- When defining criteria for evaluating energy community projects in public calls, it’s crucial to move beyond a narrow focus on technical feasibility and economic viability. While these are important factors, an overemphasis on them can inadvertently favor larger, well-resourced companies that excel in these areas. Instead, adopt a holistic approach that gives equal weight to environmental and social criteria (including its contribution to community well-being, social inclusion, job creation, energy poverty alleviation, and empowerment of marginalized groups).
- Consider incorporating specific eligibility criteria and scoring mechanisms that reward projects with strong social and environmental components, such as community engagement, social inclusion and environmental stewardship, even if they may have higher upfront costs or lower immediate financial returns.
- Provide additional support or scoring advantages to smaller, community-led initiatives to counterbalance the inherent advantages of larger corporations through simplified application processes and targeted funding streams for smaller-scale community energy projects.
- Establish dedicated funding calls specifically for energy communities or even for different categories of energy communities (CECs, RECs, citizen based, composed for a majority of local authorities, SMEs, etc.). This prevents them from having to compete with larger, more established energy companies that often have greater resources and expertise in navigating complex funding applications.
- Explicitly exclude legal entities with a dominant position in the energy market from benefiting from energy community funding schemes. This ensures that funding is directed towards genuine community-led initiatives and prevents large companies from using their market power to crowd out smaller projects.
- When allocating funding, prioritize projects with a higher proportion of citizen participation and community ownership. This ensures that funding supports initiatives that truly represent the interests of local residents and contribute to community empowerment.
- Develop robust mechanisms to prevent subsidiaries or empty corporate shells from being used by large companies to circumvent eligibility criteria and gain access to funding or benefits intended for genuine community-led initiatives. This could include conducting thorough checks on ownership structures and control mechanisms to identify any links to large energy corporations or other dominant actors.

3. BAN MISLEADING CLAIMS AND “CITIZEN WASHING”

- Enforce existing laws against misleading advertising, with a specific focus on preventing the misuse of the “energy community” label. Prohibit the use of this term for projects that do not meet the established legal criteria for genuine energy communities.
- Require clear and prominent disclosures in all advertisements and marketing materials for energy community projects, such as the level of community ownership and control, the governance structure and decision-making processes and how benefits are shared among community members.
- Establish significant penalties for companies that engage in false or misleading advertising related to energy communities. This could include fines, legal action, injunctions to cease misleading advertising, and the revocation of permits or licenses.
- Develop clear and comprehensive guidance for companies on permissible advertising claims related to energy communities. This guidance should provide specific examples of acceptable and unacceptable practices, helping companies to comply with regulations and avoid misleading consumers.
- Launch public education campaigns to inform consumers about the characteristics of genuine energy communities and how to identify misleading advertising. This could include online resources, informational brochures, workshops, and media campaigns.

4. ENSURE THE NON COMMERCIAL PURPOSE

- Policy and regulatory frameworks should emphasize that the primary purpose of energy communities is to deliver environmental, social, and economic benefits to their members and the local area, rather than solely focusing on financial gains. For instance, requiring energy communities to include provisions in their founding statutes or articles of association indicating how profit will either be a subordinate objective or otherwise prohibited.
- To safeguard the community-focused nature of energy initiatives, guidelines should be established to clarify the extent to which profit is permissible within these communities while ensuring that it is subordinate to social and environmental benefits. While limiting permissible legal forms to those aligned with non-profit or cooperative models (e.g., cooperatives, non-profit associations) can be an option in some cases, profit (with limits) could be allowed to some extent to avoid restricting energy communities to solely NGOs or charities. This flexibility enables the development of diverse, sustainable business models, empowering communities to thrive while maintaining their core focus on community benefit.
- Restrict the definition of energy communities to those based on co-ownership of assets. While third party CSC models are a valid form of decentralization, they should not qualify to be eligible to receive the same types of specific incentives and benefits designed for energy communities.

5. GUARANTEE OPEN AND VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

- Energy communities should establish clear, transparent, and non-discriminatory criteria for membership. These criteria should apply to all potential members, including anchor members or owners of the spaces where renewable energy installations will be located. It’s essential to consider factors beyond financial capacity, such as geographic location, demonstrated commitment to community goals, and potential contributions to social and environmental objectives. For instance, prioritize the use of municipal rooftops or publicly owned spaces for renewable energy installations over industrial sites, as this can contribute to broader community benefits and access.
- Actively encourage the participation of diverse stakeholders, including residential consumers, small businesses, non-profit organizations, and vulnerable households. This ensures balanced representation and prevents the dominance of large players or specific interest groups. Consider implementing outreach strategies to specifically target and encourage the participation of underrepresented groups, seeking that the energy community reflects the diversity of the local community.
- Avoid setting excessively high financial barriers to entry, which could exclude low-income households or smaller entities from participating.
- Explore alternative funding mechanisms that minimize upfront investment requirements for members. This can help to ensure broader participation and prevent financial barriers from excluding individuals or groups from joining the energy community. Consider options such as deferred payment schemes, where members contribute over time; loan-financed projects, where the community secures loans to cover upfront costs; or sliding scale fees based on income level, ensuring that membership is affordable for everyone.
- Develop a clear and balanced legal framework for managing membership exits. This framework should include transparent procedures for members who wish to leave the energy community, reasonable notice periods, and fair asset valuation methods to determine the value of a departing member’s share. Ensure that the process for leaving the community is straightforward and accessible to all members.

6. DEFEND THE ELIGIBILITY TO PARTICIPATE

- Explicitly exclude subsidiaries of large energy corporations from participating in RECs, even if they seemingly meet other eligibility criteria. This prevents large companies from circumventing rules and exerting undue influence through subsidiary involvement.
- Prioritize collaboration with companies that are aligned with similar principles to those established for energy communities, such as cooperatives or other entities run by economic and social economy criteria.
- Where crucial expertise (grid connection, financing) is unavailable elsewhere, engage large corporations only on a strictly contractual basis for services, without granting them membership or shareholder status in the energy community, thus denying them voting rights.
- Allow participation of entities like existing RECs and CECs and their subsidiaries in energy communities even if their primary activity is energy, provided their ownership, transparency, and community alignment are verified. This recognizes the valuable expertise these entities can offer while ensuring they operate under the same community-focused principles.
- Develop clear guidelines and thresholds for “incidental” energy activities. This helps differentiate between companies whose primary business is energy and those with secondary energy-related activities, ensuring that RECs maintain their community-driven focus.
- Provide clear guidance and support to energy communities on how to access necessary expertise without compromising their autonomy or community focus. This could include developing resources and training programs, facilitating knowledge sharing between communities through one stop shops, and promoting the growth of specialized service providers within the social economy sector.

7. ENABLE EFFECTIVE CONTROL BY THE CITIZENS

- Establish a robust definition of “effective control” that goes beyond simple majority ownership of the General Assembly or main representative body and considers factors such as voting rights, board representation, and influence over key decisions.
- Avoid options like guaranteed seats on the Board or similar to prevent large corporations or external actors from dominating community governance.
- Mandate that energy community governing documents clearly define how control and decision-making power are distributed among members. This includes specifying membership rights, outlining the governance structure and decision-making procedures, and establishing dispute resolution mechanisms.
- Ensure that companies controlling energy communities are not subsidiaries of, or controlled by, large corporations or companies whose primary activity is energy (with the exception of other RECs and CECs).
- Prioritize local control in RECs by defining “proximity” in a way that balances local ownership with the need for broader participation and access to expertise. Ensure that those most affected by renewable energy projects have a decisive voice in their operation.

8. PROTECT THE AUTONOMY PRINCIPLE

- Implement a “one member, one vote” system in the general assembly or equivalent decision-making body. This ensures that all members have an equal say in the direction of the energy community, regardless of their investment level or ownership stake.
- Introduce caps on the percentage of shares any single member can hold. This prevents any individual or entity from gaining excessive control over the energy community and ensures a more equitable distribution of ownership.
- Establish minimum participation quotas for local citizens in both membership and decision-making bodies. This ensures that the energy community remains rooted in the local community and that decisions reflect the interests of local residents. Consider setting a minimum threshold for local residents’ representation on the board of directors or other governing bodies.
- Develop and implement clear and transparent decision-making procedures that ensure all members have access to information and opportunities to participate in the decision-making process, such as open meetings (hold regular open meetings where members can discuss issues, propose ideas, and vote on key decisions), accessible information (make all relevant information about the energy community’s activities, finances, and governance readily available to all members), and incorporate member’s input (establish mechanisms for gathering and incorporating member input into decision-making, such as surveys, consultations, and working groups).
- Establish term limits for leadership positions, such as board members or executive directors, to prevent the concentration of power and ensure regular turnover. This promotes fresh perspectives and prevents any individual or group from dominating the decision-making process over long periods.

- Prioritize community-based funding sources, such as crowdfunding, cooperative loans, or local investment schemes, to reduce reliance on external investors or financial institutions that may exert undue influence.
- Explore alternative financing models that align with the community-focused principles of energy communities, such as revolving loan funds, community bonds, or ethical investment partnerships.
- Invest in developing internal expertise within the energy community to reduce reliance on external consultants or service providers. This could include providing training opportunities for members, hiring staff with relevant skills, or establishing partnerships with knowledge-sharing networks.
- Participate in and contribute to knowledge-sharing networks with other energy communities to exchange best practices, learn from each other’s experiences, and collectively build capacity.
- Mandate full transparency in all collaboration agreements with external actors, including clear disclosure of all terms and conditions, financial arrangements, and potential conflicts of interest.
- Explicitly prohibit clauses in collaboration agreements that grant external actors control over the energy community’s decision-making processes, governance structure, or strategic direction.
- Prioritize short-term contracts with external collaborators, with clearly defined scopes of work and limitations on their involvement in the energy community’s internal affairs.
- Establish transparent and objective criteria for selecting external collaborators, ensuring that decisions are based on merit, community benefit, and alignment with the energy community’s values.
- During the transposition of EU directives into national legislation, explicitly extend the principle of autonomy to CECs like some countries/regions did (France and Brussels, for instance). This ensures that CECs, like RECs, operate democratically and in the best interests of their members, preventing undue influence by large energy corporations or other external actors.

9. PROVIDE MECHANISMS OF CONTROL

- Require all energy communities to register with a designated public authority, such as a Social Economy registry or a dedicated energy community registry. This allows for ongoing monitoring of membership composition, financial activities, and compliance with regulations.
- Establish independent regulatory bodies with the mandate and resources to effectively monitor and enforce energy community regulations, including the compliance with all the principles.
- Grant specific inspection powers to regulatory bodies to verify compliance with eligibility criteria and other regulations. Ensure that these bodies have the authority to investigate complaints, conduct audits, take enforcement action and penalties against any violations, including the authority to enforce advertising regulations and issue cease-and-desist orders, and impose penalties.

Section 5

CONCLUSIONS

This report has delved into the intricate world of energy communities in Europe, exploring their potential to revolutionize the energy landscape and empower local citizens. While the promise of these initiatives is undeniable, a significant challenge threatens their success: corporate capture. This phenomenon, where large energy companies leverage their resources and influence to gain control of community energy projects, casts a shadow over the democratization of energy production.

This report has delved into the intricate world of energy communities in Europe, exploring their potential to revolutionize the energy landscape and empower local citizens. While the promise of these initiatives is undeniable, a significant challenge threatens their success: corporate capture. This phenomenon, where large energy companies leverage their resources and influence to gain control of community energy projects, casts a shadow over the democratization of energy production.

Our investigation has uncovered a **complex web of vulnerabilities that enable corporate capture**. Ambiguous definitions and inconsistent implementation of EU directives across Member States create fertile ground for exploitation. Large energy companies, adept at navigating regulatory loopholes, can readily exploit these inconsistencies to their advantage. They may leverage financial incentives, engage in misleading advertising campaigns that portray them as champions of community energy, and even influence policymaking to serve their own interests.

The **consequences of corporate capture are far-reaching and detrimental** to the very essence of community energy. It can lead to the erosion of community ownership and control, diminish social and environmental benefits, and ultimately erode public trust in the energy transition. When energy communities become dominated by corporate interests, the original vision of citizen empowerment and local self-determination is compromised.

To counter this threat, a multi-pronged strategy is required, encompassing both proactive measures by energy communities and robust regulatory frameworks. Energy communities must prioritize transparency and accountability in their governance structures, ensuring that decision-making power truly resides with their members. They need to **actively cultivate internal expertise and diversify funding sources to reduce reliance on external actors**. Crucially, they must remain vigilant against subtle forms of corporate influence, actively advocating for their interests and holding policymakers accountable.

On the policy front, **clear and concrete definitions of energy communities are paramount**. These definitions must include detailed enough requirements to emphasize **genuine community ownership, local control, and democratic governance, leaving no room for ambiguity or exploitation**. Robust monitoring and enforcement mechanisms are essential to ensure compliance and prevent corporate capture. Financial incentives should be designed to prioritize community-led initiatives, with safeguards in place to prevent corporate dominance. Furthermore, regulations must combat misleading advertising, requiring clear and transparent disclosure of information to empower consumers and prevent them from being misled by “greenwashing” tactics.

Beyond these specific measures, a broader shift in perspective is needed. We must recognize that the **energy transition is not merely a technological challenge but also a social and political one**. It presents a unique opportunity to reimagine our relationship with energy, shifting from a centralized, profit-driven model to a more decentralized and community-centric one. Energy communities embody this vision, offering a pathway towards a more democratic and equitable energy system.

However, the success of this vision hinges on our collective commitment to safeguarding the integrity of energy communities. This **requires a concerted effort from policymakers, regulators, energy communities, and citizens alike**. By fostering a policy environment that prioritizes genuine community empowerment and by empowering communities to protect their autonomy, we can unlock the transformative potential of community energy.

By ensuring that energy communities remain truly community-led, we can pave the way for a future where energy production is more democratized, local communities are empowered, and the benefits of the energy transition are more distributed than in the current model. This report serves as a call to action, urging stakeholders across Europe to join forces in safeguarding the integrity of energy communities and building a more democratic and sustainable energy future.

Section 11

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